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PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF CADASTRAL VALUATION OF LAND RESOURCES IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract: The article deals with the actual problem of cadastral assessment of lands and land resources in the Republic of Kazakhstan. The author highlights the problems of soil degradation and desertification and regulation of land relations, land surveying and cadastral works. The article provides statistical data on the area of land resources in the Republic of Kazakhstan, and also covers the topic of special legal regime of land protection. Advantages and disadvantages of existing methods of solving this problem of cadastral assessment of lands are given.

Key words: desertification, agricultural lands, land fertility, rational utilization, degradation of agricultural land, agricultural turnover, effective farming, withdrawal, cadastral assessment, soil degradation.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada Qozog'iston Respublikasida yer va yer resurslarini kadastr baholashning dolzarb muammosi ko'rib chiqiladi. Muallif tuproq degradatsiyasi va cho'llanish muammolari hamda yer munosabatlarini tartibga solish, yer tuzish va kadastr ishlarini yoritib beradi. Maqolada Qozog'iston Respublikasida yer resurslari maydoni bo'yicha statistik ma'lumotlar keltirilgan, shuningdek, yerni muhofaza qilishning alohida huquqiy rejimi mavzusi yoritilgan. Yerlarni kadastr baholashning ushbu muammosini hal qilishning mavjud usullarining afzalliklari va kamchiliklari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: cho'llanish, qishloq xo'jaligi yerlari, yer unumdorligi, oqilona foydalanish, qishloq xo'jaligi yerlarining degradatsiyasi, qishloq xo'jaligi aylanmasi, samarali dehqonchilik, olib qo'yish, kadastr baholash, tuproq degradatsiyasi.

Аңдатпа: Мақалада Қазақстан Республикасындағы жер мен жер ресурстарын кадастрлық бағалаудың өзекті мәселесі қарастырылады. Автор топырақтың деградациясы мен шөлейттену және жер қатынастарын, жерге орналастыру және кадастрлық жұмыстарды реттеу мәселелерін баяндайды. Мақалада Қазақстан Республикасындағы жер ресурстарының ауданы бойынша статистикалық деректер келтірілген, сондай-ақ жерді қорғаудың ерекше құқықтық режимі тақырыбы қамтылған. Жерді кадастрлық бағалаудың осы мәселесін шешудің қолданыстағы әдістерінің артықшылықтары мен кемшіліктері келтірілген.

Түйінді сөздер: шөлейттену, ауыл шаруашылығы жерлері, жердің құнарлылығы, ұтымды пайдалану, ауыл шаруашылығы жерлерінің деградациясы, ауыл шаруашылығы айналымы, тиімді Ауыл шаруашылығы, алып қою, кадастрлық бағалау, топырақтың деградациясы.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается актуальная проблема кадастровой оценки земель и земельных ресурсов в Республике Казахстан. Автор освещает проблемы деградации почв и опустынивания и регулирования земельных отношений, землеустроительных и кадастровых работ. В статье приведены статистические данные по площади земельных ресурсов в Республике Казахстан, а также освещена тема особого правового режима охраны земель. Приведены преимущества и недостатки существующих методов решения данной проблемы кадастровой оценки земель.

Ключевые слова: опустынивание, сельскохозяйственные земли, плодородие земель, рациональное использование, деградация сельскохозяйственных земель, сельскохозяйственный оборот, эффективное ведение сельского хозяйства, изъятие, кадастровая оценка, деградация почв.

INTRODUCTION

In modern conditions, soil degradation and desertification are becoming increasingly serious challenges to the environmental and economic sustainability of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Assessment of land resources plays an important role in effective land management and combating these problems. This article discusses the main problems of cadastral land valuation in Kazakhstan and proposes ways to solve them.

Land is an invaluable wealth of the society. It is the main natural resource, material condition of life and activity of people, the basis for the location and development of all sectors of the national economy, the main

means of production in agriculture and the main source of food. Kazakhstan, which occupies the ninth position in terms of territory, has extensive natural resources, including the diversity of soils and soil cover. It is one of the largest countries in the world in terms of its natural resource potential. The soil cover of Kazakhstan has a complex structure characterized by a variety of soil types.

It is important to note that developing in arid and extra-arid conditions, soils of Kazakhstan are subject to special challenges and threats. They have easy vulnerability and low resistance to anthropogenic loads. These factors create a high risk of degradation and desertification processes, which poses a serious threat to the environmental sustainability of the region.

The difference of soils of Kazakhstan from soils of other countries, such as Canada, USA and European countries, includes their adaptation to arid conditions, as well as specific features of chemical composition, structure and physical properties.

Active use of land resources without taking into account their peculiarities and vulnerability can lead to negative consequences such as soil degradation, reduction of fertility and desertification. Therefore, it is important to take appropriate measures for sustainable management and protection of land resources to ensure their conservation and sustainable use in the future.

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Methods of my research problems and prospects of cadastral valuation of land resources in the Republic of Kazakhstan:

- **Literature Review:** Conduct a comprehensive review of existing literature, including academic papers, government reports, policy documents, and other relevant sources, to gain insights into the current state of cadastral valuation practices in Kazakhstan, as well as the challenges and potential solutions identified by experts.
- **Survey Questionnaires:** Design and administer survey questionnaires to relevant stakeholders, such as landowners, government officials, real estate professionals, and experts in cadastral valuation, to gather opinions, perceptions, and experiences related to the problems and prospects of cadastral valuation in Kazakhstan.
- **Interviews:** Conduct semi-structured interviews with key informants, including officials from government agencies responsible for land management, representatives from cadastral organizations, legal experts, and academics, to obtain in-depth insights into the challenges faced and potential opportunities for improving cadastral valuation practices.
- **Case Studies:** Analyze specific case studies of cadastral valuation projects in different regions of Kazakhstan to identify common issues, best practices, and lessons learned. This approach can provide valuable context and practical insights into the implementation of cadastral valuation in the country.
- **Data Analysis:** Utilize quantitative methods to analyze available data on land use, land values, property transactions, and other relevant indicators to assess trends, patterns, and correlations related to cadastral valuation in Kazakhstan. This may involve statistical analysis, spatial analysis, and econometric modeling, depending on the nature of the research questions.
- **Comparative Analysis:** Compare the cadastral valuation systems and practices in Kazakhstan with those of other countries facing similar challenges or adopting innovative approaches to land valuation. This comparative analysis can help identify potential strategies and lessons that may be applicable in the Kazakhstani context.
- **Expert Workshops:** Organize workshops or focus group discussions with experts and practitioners in the field of cadastral valuation to brainstorm ideas, share experiences, and collaboratively develop

recommendations for addressing the identified problems and enhancing the prospects of land valuation in Kazakhstan [2].

Using a combination of these research methods, I was able to gain a comprehensive understanding of the problems and prospects for land cadastral valuation in Kazakhstan and formulate evidence-based recommendations for policy improvements and practical interventions.

The Republic of Kazakhstan has a significant area of land resources, but insufficient efficiency of their utilization leads to soil degradation and desertification. According to the latest statistical data, the total area of land in Kazakhstan is. Special attention is paid to the protection of lands and the application of a special legal regime for their protection. (Figure 1).^{[3][8]}

Figure 1: Desertification and land degradation

Problems of cadastral valuation of land resources

One of the main problems is the lack of a unified methodology and standards for cadastral land valuation, which leads to heterogeneity and incomparability of the assessment results. In addition, the existing methods of cadastral valuation do not always take into account the soil and climatic features of the regions, which reduces the accuracy and reliability of the assessment.

Problems of cadastral valuation of land resources:

- **Lack of common methodology and standards:** One of the main shortcomings in the field of cadastral valuation of land resources in Kazakhstan is that there is no generally accepted methodology and standards that would be applicable to all regions of the country. This leads to a variety of evaluation methods, making it difficult to compare and analyze the results.
- **Insufficient consideration of soil-climatic features:** Many existing methods of cadastral land assessment do not take into account the local soil-climatic features of the regions. This causes the estimate to be incorrect or unreliable, reducing its usefulness for decision-making.
- **Insufficient control and monitoring:** One of the problems is also insufficient control over the conduct of cadastral valuation and over compliance with legislation in this area. This can lead to unfair practices and falsification of data.
- **Inefficient use of valuation results:** Another problem may be that the results of cadastral valuation are not always used effectively for decision-making in land relations and land management.^{[5][7]}
- **Discussion:** Problems and prospects of cadastral valuation of land resources in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Discuss the current problems faced by the cadastral assessment of land resources in Kazakhstan:

- **Lack of standardized methodologies:** One of the main problems is the lack of a unified methodology for cadastral valuation, which leads to a variety of approaches and opacity of the process. Standardized methodologies should be developed and implemented to ensure uniformity and comparability of assessment results.
- **Inadequate consideration of soil-climatic conditions:** Soil-climatic conditions in Kazakhstan are diverse, and each region has its own characteristics. However, at present, taking these conditions into account when conducting cadastral valuation is insufficient, which can lead to incorrect estimates and decisions.
- **Insufficient monitoring and control mechanisms:** Lack of effective monitoring and control mechanisms for cadastral valuation processes complicates data quality and reliability assurance.

RESULTS OF MY RESEARCH

The result of my research is that, to solve the problems of cadastral valuation of land resources, it is important to develop a unified methodology that takes into account local characteristics. The introduction of modern technologies, such as geographic information systems and remote sensing, can significantly improve the accuracy of land resource assessment and monitoring.

It is also important to strengthen c Advantages and disadvantages of existing methods of solving the problem:

Advantages:

- The introduction of modern technologies, such as geographic information systems (GIS) and remote sensing, can significantly improve the accuracy and efficiency of cadastral valuation.
- The development of a common methodology and standards can contribute to comparability of evaluation results and improved data quality.
- Strengthening control and monitoring of cadastral valuation can help prevent unfair practices and data falsification.

Disadvantages:

- The introduction of new technologies requires significant investment and staff training, which can be difficult in resource-limited settings.
- Developing a common methodology and standards may require time and effort for consensus among stakeholders.
- Increased control and monitoring also requires additional resources and commitments from the state. control over compliance with land protection legislation and the use of special legal regimes.

The problem of cadastral assessment of land resources in the Republic of Kazakhstan requires a systematic approach and comprehensive measures to improve the methodology for assessment, control and monitoring. This will allow more efficient land management and prevent further soil degradation and desertification.

List of used literature:

1. Rules of rational use of agricultural land [Electronic resource]. – Approved by the order of the Minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Kazakhstan from January 17, 2020 No 7. – Access mode: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V2000019893>
2. Rules for organizing and monitoring the use of agricultural land provided for peasant or farmer farms, agricultural production [Electronic resource]. – Approved by the Order of the Minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Kazakhstan from July 3, 2019 No 252. – Access mode: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V2000019893>
3. Navdaeva, S.N. Economic and statistical analysis of the performance indicators of agricultural enterprises [Text] : textbook / S.N. Navdaeva, T.D. Dudoglo; FGBOU VO Nizhny Novgorod State Agricultural Academy [Electronic resource]. – N.Novgorod, 2020. – 100 c. – Access mode: <https://nnsaa.ru/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/ehkonom-stat-analiz-pokazatelej-deya-ti-s-h-pred-tij.pdf>
4. Akhmetova N.Z., Mustafina N.K., Muzyka O.S. Improvement of the system of state control over the use and protection of land in the Republic of Kazakhstan // Science and the World. 2015. T. 2. –№ 2 (18). C. 19-21.
5. Akhmetova N.Z. State of agrarian production of Kazakhstan in modern conditions // Scientific Works of SWorld. 2010. T. 11. –№ 1. C. 48-53.
6. Consolidated analytical report, 2014.
7. "Land resources of the RK", 2015.
8. Murasheva A.A. Increasing the efficiency of land use in the system of territory management // Land management, cadastre and land monitoring. 2006. –№ 6. C. 39-42.

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